

Is big data driving a paradigm shift in precision agriculture?

Megan Z Cushnahan*¹, Brennon A Wood¹, Ian J Yule¹
Institute of Agriculture and Environment, Massey University, New Zealand

Abstract

In recent years there has been considerable debate about the significance of the digital explosion for precision agriculture (PA). Much of the discussion focuses on whether the arrival of big data signals the emergence of or need for a new paradigm. Answering such questions requires historical analysis. In order to determine where PA research is now and where it may go in the future, we need to understand where it has come from and how it has developed. This paper brings together a new collection of statistics depicting recent trends in PA and the structure of scientific production based on bibliometric data from Scopus and other selected sources. The results should provide a valuable resource of bibliometric indicators for researchers and policy-makers working in the field of PA.

Background

Previous research has attempted to classify outputs from PA research, however these studies tend to focus on the equipment used, rather than the sphere of application and data-related attributes of technologies (Douthwaite, Keatinge, & Park, 2001; Nowak, 1997; Griffin, Lowenberg-DeBoer, Lambert, Peone, Payne, Daberkow, 2004; Griffin, 2011; Sunding & Zilberman, 2001). This study capitalises on the rapid advances in the accessibility and quality of information sources such as Elsevier's Scopus, Google Scholar and Web of Science (OECD, 2016). While some previous bibliometric work (Liu, Guo, & Guan, 2010) has been undertaken in the PA space, it has been limited in scale and scope. This paper reports on the initial findings of an on-going study where a very large dataset of publications has been created and coded, and aggregate analyses undertaken to discover shifts in publication volumes and content over time.

Methods

The researchers are undertaking a scientometric study of a longitudinal dataset comprising PA publications, including scientific articles and conference proceedings from a wide range of peer-reviewed sources. Hess (1997) describes the scientometric approach as the "quantitative study of science, communication in science, and science policy". The dataset was initially populated using searches of Scopus (Elsevier) databases. Searches were not initially restricted by publication date or publication type. Scopus' databases were searched using the following search types: TS= ("precision agriculture"), TS= ("precision farming"), TS= ("site-specific agriculture"), TS= ("site-specific farming"), TS= ("soil-specific agriculture"), TS= ("soil-specific farming"), TS= ("digital agriculture") and TS= ("digital farming").

The dataset includes the entire *Precision Agriculture Journal* catalogue and papers presented at the following conferences were included (where available):

- International Conference for Precision Agriculture (1998, 2000, 2008, 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016)
- Proceedings of First Workshop in Soil Specific Crop Management (1993)
- European Precision Agriculture Conferences (where data available).

Each scientific publication is treated as an individual unit of analysis and is stored in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Data included the following categories: Title, Authors, Year, Source title, Volume, Issue, Article Number, Page start, Page end, Page count, Cited by, Affiliations, Authors with affiliations, Abstract, Author Keywords, References, Document Type, Source and EI. All records were checked for relevance and duplicates removed. Citation information for each record was accessed from Google Scholar.

Each publication is coded for their main subjects (not just mentions) to the following domains: country of first author, crop type, enabling technology, geolocation and location in the value chain. For crop type, the research crop was coded to a publication if it was used as a subject in the experiment(s) or if a technology was designed to be applied to a specified crop.

Records were coded to a certain technology if it was used in experiments or if it was the focus of the study (not simply mentioned). For the purposes of this paper, trends in the popularity of 'data intensive' technologies were categorised. The authors consider a technology to be data intensive if it is capable of creating a concentration of data for a single geospatial location (may also be spectrally-intensive) The authors classified the following technologies as data-intensive; electromagnetic induction technologies (EMI technologies), robotics, machine vision, wireless sensor networks (WSNs), hyperspectral sensors, multispectral sensors, light detection and ranging sensors (LiDAR).

Results

A dataset of 11,597 published papers in the field of precision agriculture were collected. A small number of papers listed in the database were published as early as the 1950s (Gunther & March, 1956; Stolzy, Cahoon, & Szuszkiewicz, 1957) on topics still considered contemporary, such as site-specific irrigation based on soil moisture monitoring. The number of relevant scientific publications has dramatically increased over the past twenty years from 207 in 1996 to 1005 in 2016 (Figure 1), with an annual mean growth rate of 5.5% for that period.

The dataset was analysed to create several key bibliometric indicators that provide credible evidence that precision agriculture research is changing in terms of the increased diversity of locations and crops to which PA tools are being applied. The data signposts dramatic changes in PA including:

- Global distribution of research (country of first author)
- Increasing diversity of crops researched
- Distribution of topics of researched

Preliminary data analyses also suggest that the data economy of PA research may be changing due to:

- Increase in research in data-intensive technologies
- Greater diversity and use of remote sensing data collection platforms

Geolocation of research

The initial findings of the study are that the global distribution of scientific production has become far more diverse in the past thirty years. In 1996, first authors from only 22 countries published PA papers, a figure that had more than tripled to 72 in 2016. Much of the growth in global scientific publication output has been driven by new players, including China, India, Spain and Brazil, who collectively have seen their share of global publications (including conferences) rise from 1% in 1996 to 38% in 2016 (first authors), see Figure 2.

Figure 1. Annual evolution of published papers (all categories), 1956–2016

Figure 2. Share of precision agriculture publications, 1996–2016

The USA dominated the field of PA research until the mid-2000s, producing over half of all global publications in the late 1990s. The USA has since seen its share of first authors gradually reduce to 20% of publications in 2016; this pattern that may point to a shift in US collaboration practices or signpost an overall decline in world influence. While the USA's share of the global outputs has significantly decreased, this is mainly due to the massive growth in global outputs; the actual number of USA publications has remained relatively stable. It is important to note however, that the USA numbers spike biennially due to the influence of the International Conference for Precision Agriculture (ICPA), where the USA is significantly over-represented, e.g. in 2016, USA first authors presented 43% of the papers at the ICPA conference, some three times their global share of journal publications (13%).

Diversity of crops researched

Rapid growth in scientific outputs from an increasingly diverse pool of researchers has led to a large rise in the diversity of crops researched by PA researchers. The number of crops researched has quadrupled in the last 20 years from 22 in 1996 to 88 in 2016, as researchers apply PA techniques and technologies to new crops and environments. Arable crops, e.g. corn (25%), wheat (13%), soybeans (9%) and cotton (6%), dominated the research effort in the late 1990s, with a 70% share of crops researched (all major arable crops on average, 1996-1999). While these crops continue to be widely researched, by 2016 crops such as rice (8%), viticulture (5%), potatoes (2%), sugarcane (2%) and tree crops (6%) were increasingly the focus of research outputs. In 2016, the combined share of arable crops had reduced to 51% of crops researched (including corn (18%), wheat (4%), soybeans (4%), barley (4%) and cotton (4%)). Initial results of the study also suggest that PA techniques and technologies are increasingly being applied to livestock research, especially from 2004 onwards.

Is the data generated by precision agriculture technologies changing?

It is highly relevant to establish whether the data characteristics of the technologies used by PA researchers are changing. Researchers such as Sonka and IFAMR (2014) have previously explored the notion that the nature of data used by PA researchers is being transformed, suggesting that in order for value to be extracted from new datasets that may contain massive amounts of highly variable data researchers will need to be able to process large quantities of data quickly. Importantly, some PA researchers have identified that technologies with different data characteristics may have different adoption trends (Shaw & Willers, 2006), indicating that a robust typology may be a useful guide for future research on technology development and diffusion strategies (Griffin, 2004; Mulla, 2013). To ascertain how the data economy of PA research may be changing, the dataset was explored to identify shifts in the use of data-intensive technologies and/or methods (Cushnahan, 2016). Preliminary results indicate that there has indeed been a significant shift towards data-

intensive technologies and methods in recent years (Figure 3). Remote sensing technologies such as multispectral and hyperspectral sensors, LiDAR and EMI technologies have increasingly become the focus of scientific publications, rising from 43 (combined total) in 2000 to 163 in 2016 (note that in some instances a publication may be coded to more than one technology).

Figure 3. The rise of data-intensive technologies in precision agriculture research, 1996–2016

Early results of the study highlight the rapid rise of wireless sensor networks in late 2000s, as the technology became more mainstream and cost-effective. Robotics and machine vision have become more commonly used in PA research outputs. Interestingly, publication numbers on EMI technologies, which were relatively stable since the early 2000s, have declined in recent years. The authors hypothesise that EMI research has decreased due to it becoming a ‘mainstream’ technology that is less appealing to researchers interested in studying emerging technologies.

Remote sensing platforms

Agriculture researchers traditionally made field measurements proximally, e.g. soil testing, although aerial photography was also used (Burger, 1996; Flowers, Weisz, & Heiniger, 2000; Franzen, Reitmeier, Giles, & Cattanach, 1999). In addition to understanding the intensity of data collected by researchers, the authors were interested in how PA data is captured utilising satellite, airborne, UAVs (UAS) and proximal platforms, which includes both static and mobile proximal platforms.

Analysis of the dataset indicates that the use of satellites has grown since the early 2000s and they remain the most widely reported remote sensing platform in PA today, see Figure 4. The use of sensors mounted on UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) rocketed from 2013, largely driven by the rapidly reducing cost of UAV units (Matese et al., 2015; Toth & Józków, 2016). Interestingly, proximal data collection was much more widely reported during this time, and while about a quarter of this growth can be attributed to the increase in publications overall, a review of the dataset shows that proximal sensing is often being used to ground truth data collected using UAVs and satellites. Unlike all the other remote sensing platforms that have become more widely used in recent years, airborne sensing platforms remain relatively unpopular in PA research, most likely due to the capital cost of entry remaining high (Toth & Józków, 2016).

Figure 4. Remote sensing data collection platforms, 1996–2016

Discussion

The limited typology research undertaken in PA previously has primarily focussed on equipment rather than the sphere of application and no agreed typologies have emerged for PA to date. In this study, we aim to make some advance by analysing technologies in holistic terms, including the data profiles and application domain to more fully understand the character and paradigmatic extent of shifts occurring in PA research.

The data analysis reveals that PA research has changed dramatically over the past 20 years. Originally dominated by the USA and the crops grown there, the research focus is far more diverse in 2016. Now a truly global field of study, researchers are applying PA techniques and technologies to a diverse range of crops throughout the world. An interesting take-home message is that whilst the USA's market share of publications has declined, it still dominates some of the major conferences in the field, including the ICPA; the biennial spike in the USA's publication outputs is largely due to the USA's strong presence at this event. It could be argued that the diversity of authors presenting at some of these conferences is no longer representative of the wider PA research community. This highlights a key challenge for the sector, which is to identify ways to make conferences more inclusive for international researchers.

A key trend identified is rapid expansion in data-intensive technologies in the past decade, sign-posting a shift from the historically-dominant topics of soil testing and machinery-focused research to remote sensing. The data collection platforms used by precision agriculture researchers is also changing, and the study points to a move from ground-based measurement to sensing from the air.

This study not only highlights how PA research is changing, but also how it is not. Many of the papers included in the database mentioned the poor uptake of precision agriculture technology; however fewer than 0.1% of papers focussed on PA technology adoption in 2016. Even fewer articles were indexed that discussed how researchers can deal with the changing data economy, although several of the articles discussed the challenges that lie ahead for PA researchers.

Conclusion

Using scientometrics as an assessment technique, this study provides insight into the increasing complexity and diversity of PA research. Preliminary results indicate that the global distribution of first authors has changed dramatically. Importantly, the study signposts a widening sphere of application in PA research and a trend towards data-intensive technologies. The results will help those engaged in PA research to better prepare for the opportunities and challenges ahead.

References

- Burger B 1996. ADAR Digital aerial photography applications in precision farming. *Precision Agriculture* 905–905.
- Cushnahan MZ, Wood BA, Yule IJ, Wilson R 2016. Surplus science and a non-linear model for the development of precision agriculture technology. Paper presented at the 13th International Conference on Precision Agriculture, St Louis, Missouri, USA.
<https://www.ispag.org/proceedings/?action=abstract&id=1922>
- Douthwaite B, Keatinge J, Park J 2001. Why promising technologies fail: the neglected role of user innovation during adoption. *Research Policy* 30(5): 819–836.
- Flowers M, Weisz R, Heiniger R 2000. Aerial photographic determination of nitrogen application timing and rate recommendations in winter wheat. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Precision Agriculture, Bloomington, Minnesota, USA. 16–19 July 2000.
- Franzen DW, Reitmeier L, Giles JF, Cattanaach AC 1999. Aerial photography and satellite imagery to detect deep soil nitrogen levels in potato and sugarbeet. *Precision Agriculture (precisionagric4a)* Pp. 281–290.
- Griffin T, Lowenberg-DeBoer J, Lambert DM, Peone J, Payne T, Daberkow SG 2004. Adoption, profitability, and making better use of precision farming data. Staff paper (04-06).
- Gunther F, March R 1956. Instruments in agriculture-the pesticides field. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 4(7): 598–602.
- Hess DJ 1997. *Science studies: An advanced introduction*: NYU press.
- Liu A, Guo Y, Guan R 2010. The research status on precision agriculture by use of bibliometric analysis from three databases. Paper presented at World Automation Congress (WAC), 2010.
- Matese A, Toscano P, Di Gennaro SF, Genesio L, Vaccari FP, Primicerio J, Gioli B 2015. Intercomparison of UAV, aircraft and satellite remote sensing platforms for precision viticulture. *Remote Sensing* 7(3): 2971–2990.
- Mulla DJ 2013. Twenty five years of remote sensing in precision agriculture: Key advances and remaining knowledge gaps. *Biosystems Engineering* 114(4): 358–371.
- Nowak P 1997. A sociological analysis of site-specific management. *The State of Site-Specific Management for Agriculture (thestateofsites)*. Pp. 397–422.
- Shaw DR, Willers JL 2006. Improving pest management with remote sensing. *Outlooks on Pest Management* 17(5): 197–201.
- Sonka S, Ifamr I 2014. Big data and the ag sector: more than lots of numbers. *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review* 17(1): 1.
- Stolzy L, Cahoon G, Szuszkiewicz T 1957. Measurement of soil moisture: Accurate instruments for measuring soil moisture conditions practical means of determining proper timing of irrigation. *California Agriculture* 11(4): 21–37.
- Toth C, Jóźków G 2016. Remote sensing platforms and sensors: A survey. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 115: 22–36.